

Salt Effect on the Unimolecular Solvolysis of *t*-Butyl Chloride

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The kinetics of solvolysis of *t*-butyl chloride has been studied in methanol-water mixtures of different compositions in presence and absence of various salts. The effects of salts on the specific rates have been examined.

The diagnostic importance of salt effect on the kinetics of certain nucleophilic substitution reactions for distinguishing the mechanism of such reactions has often been questioned¹. Contrary to the predictions of Ingold² that the salt effect should be independent of the nature of the salt, Luccas and Hammett³ and, more recently, Spieth and Olson⁴ have observed specific behaviour on the part of the salts, especially on their anions. So far, salt effects on the solvolysis of the alkyl halides have mainly been investigated in aqueous acetone solvents and only a limited number of salts, particularly the lithium salts, have been used. Salt-effect studies in common mixed solvents, like aqueous methanol or ethanol, are surprisingly rare. It has therefore been our aim to study the effect of salts on the solvolysis of alkyl halides in some of these mixed solvents and to ascertain the manner in which the effect is related to the nature of the ions and the solvent composition. In the present communication the effect of salts on the kinetics of a representative S_N1 reaction, e.g., solvolysis of *t*-butyl chloride, has been studied in aqueous methanol at two different compositions of the solvent and at two different temperatures (30° and 40°).

EXPERIMENTAL

t-Butyl chloride was prepared by the method described by Vogel⁴ and was purified by fractional distillation. A sample boiling at 51° was collected. Methanol was dried by refluxing it with magnesium methoxide and then distilling in absence of moisture.

Methanol-water mixtures were prepared by mixing weighed amounts of the pure component solvents.

Kinetic measurements were carried out at 30° and 40° in presence or absence of salts. The reaction was followed by titration of the acid, formed as a result of the solvolysis. Reaction solutions were prepared by mixing 1 ml of *t*-butyl chloride with the solvent alone

1. Olson and Halford, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 2644; Cropper and Olson, *ibid.*, 1954, 76, 5245; Späth and Olson, *ibid.*, 1955, 77, 1412; Taylor, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1853.
2. "Structure and Mechanism in Organic Chemistry", 1953, pp. 345-365.
3. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 1928.
4. "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 1948, p. 275.

or with the solvent containing appropriate amount of the added salt so as to provide a total volume of 100 ml at the respective temperature. Aliquot parts (5 ml) were diluted with acetone and then titrated with sodium hydroxide solution, using lacmoid as an indicator.

Integrated first-order rate constants were obtained graphically from the slopes of plots $\log [t\text{-BuCl}]$ vs. time. Details of a typical run are recorded in Table I. The specific rates were reproducible within 1 to 2% of their individual values. From the results of runs at 30° and 40°, activation energy, E , frequency factor, A , and entropy of activation, $\Delta S^\ddagger$, were calculated.

TABLE I

Kinetic run in presence of NaClO₄ (0.1M) at 30°

Solvent: Methanol-water (%methanol 75.93); 5ml portions titrated with 0.05*N*-NaOH.

Time (min.)	0	15	30	45	60	90	120	180	240	α
Titre (ml)	0.18	0.55	0.96	1.31	1.70	2.34	2.96	4.02	5.08	9.08
Log [<i>t</i> -BuCl]	0.949	0.931	0.910	0.889	0.868	0.829	0.787	0.704	0.662	

$$10^5 k_1 = 5.22 \text{ sec}^{-1}.$$

TABLE II

Solvolysis of t-butyl chloride in aqueous methanol.

Composition of solvents (%MeOH by wt.).	$10^5 k_1$ (sec ⁻¹) at		E , (kcal./mole).	$10^{13} A$.	$\Delta S^\ddagger$ (cal. degree ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹).
	30°.	40°.			
59.43	21.14	76.30	24.3	5.7	2.4
64.79	14.18	50.40	23.6	1.2	-0.7
70.29	8.19	27.44	22.9	2.1	-4.1
75.93	4.40	14.66	22.8	9.5	-5.7

TABLE III

Rate constants of solvolysis of t-butyl chloride in aqueous methanol in presence of added salts.

Solvent comp. (%MeOH by wt.).	Temp.	$10^5 k_1$ (sec ⁻¹) in presence of different salts (0.1 M).							
		NaClO ₄ .	NaCl.	NaBr.	KCl.	BaCl ₂ .	KI.	KBr.	NH ₄ Bi.
70.29	30°	9.64	8.00	10.03	8.84	9.99			
	40°	28.04	27.71	31.55	28.12	31.03	34.57	30.73	39.23
75.93	30°	5.10	4.97	4.44	4.97	4.57			
	40°	17.20	15.97	15.83	16.71	17.20			

DISCUSSION

The kinetic form is of first order both in presence and absence of salts and is unaffected by the change in solvent composition, *i.e.*, when the proportion of methanol is increased from 59.43 to 75.93% by weight (Table III). In all the runs, good straight line plots for $\log [t\text{-BuCl}]$ vs. time were obtained and no significant deviation from the straight line was noticed with the progress of the solvolysis. The specific reaction rate, the energy, and the entropy of activation (Table II), as determined for four different solvent compositions, are in good agreement with those found in the literature¹.

Addition of salts (0.1*M*) invariably increased the specific reaction rates (Table III) in both the solvent compositions and at both the temperatures, 30° and 40°. The magnitude of the effect observed with different salts, however, shows no apparent regularity. Sodium chloride and potassium chloride have almost the same effect and this similarity is almost maintained at both the temperature and solvent composition, but barium chloride shows an irregular salt effect, varying both with temperature and solvent composition. The last one, being a bi-univalent salt, produces a higher ionic strength in its solutions than sodium or potassium chloride, when the molar concentration of each is the same, and thus should consistently show a larger effect than those two salts, if the salt effect happens to be essentially an ionic strength effect. Although this is true both at 30° and 40° in 70.29% methanol, the results, however, appear to be anomalous in 75.93% methanol, where the effect produced by barium chloride at 30° is in fact less than that of sodium or potassium chloride; but at 40°, a reversal of order takes place, barium chloride producing a larger effect than either sodium chloride or potassium chloride. Similar is the behaviour of sodium perchlorate and sodium bromide. The result is particularly surprising in the case of sodium bromide in view of the fact that conductance measurements show that sodium chloride and sodium bromide are dissociated almost to the same extent in 76.24% (w/w) aqueous methanol⁶. The results appear to be in agreement with the recent view that salt effects are largely specific effects produced by the salts. The suggestion that these might be negative-ion effects does not seem to be generally true because the anion remaining the same, the effect is found to vary with the cation. For example, in 70.29% aqueous methanol at 40°, sodium bromide, potassium bromide, and ammonium bromide increase the specific reaction rate by 15, 12, and 43% respectively.

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5. Winstein and Fainberg, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 2770.
6. Panda *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1962, 39, 537.